

Applications of Pair Distribution Function Analyses to the Emerging Field of *Non-Ideal* Metal-Organic Framework Materials

Celia Castillo-Blas,^a José María Moreno,^a Ignacio Romero-Muñiz^a and Ana Eva Platero-Prats^{*a,b}

Received 00th January 20xx,
Accepted 00th January 20xx

DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Pair Distribution Function, PDF, analyses are emerging as a powerful tool to characterize *non-ideal* metal-organic framework (MOF) materials with compromised ordering. Although originally envisaged as crystalline porous architectures, MOFs can incorporate defects in their structures either through chemistry or mechanical stress, resulting in materials with unpredicted novel properties. Indeed, a wide variety of current *non-ideal* MOFs have disorder in their structures at some extent, thereby often lacking of crystals. Typically, PDF experiments are performed using high-energy synchrotron X-rays or neutrons to achieve a superior highly atomic resolution in short times. The PDF technique analyses both Bragg and diffuse scattering signals, simultaneously, without being restricted to crystalline materials. This characteristic make PDF analyses a powerful probe to address the structural characterization of *non-ideal* MOF materials both at the local and intermediate range scales, including under *in-situ* conditions relevant for MOF synthesis, activation and catalysis.

1. Introduction

Metal-organic framework (MOF) materials, combining designer pores and rich surface chemistries, are one of the most exciting developments in recent materials science.¹ Being composed of regular metal clusters and organic ligands, MOFs were originally envisaged as crystalline porous materials.²⁻⁵ Their fascinating reticular structures are composed of regular pores with unique shapes and sizes, exhibiting tailorable chemistries. Under optimized synthesis conditions, MOF materials are typically prepared as single crystals or crystalline powders, being their structural characterization addressed by traditional crystallographic methods based on X-ray diffraction. Conventional MOF materials are, therefore, porous structures where periodicity or ordering is retained at long-range. However, understanding the atomistic structure, both at a local- and intermediate-range, of a MOF lacking of crystals disorder is a current characterization challenge in the field.

By knowing in detail the structure of a material, one is able to better understand and tailor its properties. However, studies related to the structure of atomically-defective or amorphous matter are highly challenging – X-ray diffraction often fails to describe complex disordered or nanostructured systems. A better experimental approach for studying the atomic structure of materials where crystallinity is compromised is the Pair Distribution Function (PDF) technique, which analyses both Bragg and diffuse scattering signals, simultaneously – a PDF

experiment is performed under total scattering conditions.⁶ PDF analyses do not presume periodicity, being an ideal tool for studying amorphous and disordered materials. A PDF experiment is a direct powder diffraction experiment, but uses high-energy synchrotron X-rays or neutrons to achieve a superior highly atomic resolution in short times.^{7, 8} Contrary to X-rays which are sensitive to electron density, neutrons are scattered by nuclei. This characteristic makes neutrons the ideal PDF source to study, for instance, the location of light molecules in the MOF pores, such as water.⁹ However, due to the typically high hydrogen content of the organic linkers, MOF materials often need to be deuterated, thereby making their preparation in large quantities required for neutron diffraction experiments difficult. Therefore, X-ray synchrotron sources are usually chosen for the characterization of these materials. The PDF of a given material can be defined directly in real-space,¹⁰ in terms of atomic coordinates. It contains information about the long-range atomic order (Bragg diffraction) together with both the local- and intermediate-range structural features contained in the diffuse scattering signal (Fig. 1). Key structural information such as atomic distances, coordination numbers, and particle sizes can be extracted directly from PDF data. Furthermore, the PDF analyses do not presume periodicity, being a perfect tool for studying amorphous and disordered materials.

It should be noted that the PDF is indeed not a new technique. In fact, it has been extensively used to study glasses¹¹ and disordered oxides.¹² More lately, with the development of synchrotron methods (*i.e.* high-energy radiation and flux combined with fast collection times), the goal has been to study more challenging energy-related materials such as perovskites in solar cells¹³ and lithium-ion batteries,¹⁴ and quantum dots,¹⁵ where their nano-scale nature hinders the

^a Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049, Madrid, Spain.

^b Condensed Matter Physics Institute (IFIMAC), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

use of conventional crystallographic methods. Lately, the structure of catalytic clusters deposited through synthesis into porous architectures have been addressed combining PDF with computational studies and X-ray absorption spectroscopy.^{16,17} In the field of neutrons, PDF analyses have been proved to be a powerful method to assess water interactions⁹ as well as the location of light molecules such as N₂¹⁸ and organic catalytic reagents^{19,20} within the pores of porous materials.

Fig. 1 The PDF technique is based on total scattering experiments, typically using a high-energy X-ray synchrotron source or neutrons. It analyses both Bragg and diffuse scattering signals, simultaneously, providing powerful information at the local- and intermediate-range in defective MOF materials.

Contrary to Extended X-Ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) spectroscopy, PDF is not an element sensitive technique – it provides, “in one shot”, the entire structural information of a given material. The PDF technique retrieves direct atom-atom distances, including both bonds and interactions, without restriction to crystalline materials. The experimental data can be directly correlated with radial distribution plots from computational modelling, being the use of theory-predicted structural models a common approach to fit PDF data both in real²¹ and reciprocal spaces.²²

In this minireview, we focus on the recent advances in the use of precise PDF analyses to study *non-ideal* MOF materials, where crystallinity is highly compromised. The variety of MOF materials addressed in the following covers from non-crystalline materials such as amorphous matter, liquids and glasses; to defective-frameworks, where crystallinity is

disrupted through chemistry to tailor MOF properties towards improving their ultimate applications. We also highlight latest progress on the use of *in-situ* PDF studies to follow MOF synthesis, activation and catalytic activity under real working conditions.

2. Structural insights of *non-ideal* Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) materials

2.1. Non-crystalline and disordered MOF materials: amorphous, liquids and glasses

There is an emerging interest in exploring highly disordered MOF states due to the unexpected properties seen in these non-ideal structures. By adding defects or variations from the average atomic periodicity within MOFs, one can tune the ultimate properties of the material.²³ From a structural characterization point of view, it is important to distinguish two different disorder scenarios, depending on the propagation and scale of the defects. Long-range defects, such as the incorporation of heterogeneity through chemistry, are able to significantly modify native regular MOF porosities towards complex systems simultaneously containing micro-, meso- and macropores.²⁴ On the contrary, local defects such as vacancies or local distortions, exclusively occur at a limited short-range and do not disrupt the average MOF structure. Unexpectedly, local defects have been proved to have remarkable impact in applications where molecular interactions are key, such as conductivity²⁵ and catalysis.^{26,27} Therefore, understating the atomistic nature of defects, and correlating their structure with ultimate properties, is a current challenge in the MOF field.

In 2010, Cheetham, Bennett and co-workers introduced the concept of *amorphous MOF*.²⁸ Being one of the main characteristics of MOF materials their crystallinity, this was surely a ground-breaking idea in the field. Non-crystalline MOFs retain only the basic structural building blocks (*i.e.* secondary building units (SBUs)²⁹ and organic linkers) and connectivity of their crystalline counterparts, while lacking of long-range order.³⁰ MOF amorphization is of particular interest in areas where small particle sizes are targeted, such as in drug delivery.^{31,32} Additional, amorphous MOF systems have proved the ability of enhance the encapsulation of guest molecules within the pores.³³ A representative example is described in Fig. 2. It can be observed that the PDF profile of an amorphous UiO-66 phase in comparison with that of its crystalline counterpart, evidencing matching signals at short-range order until *ca.* 8 \AA .³⁴ This result indicates that both amorphous and crystalline UiO-66 have identical local structures.

In 2014, Goodwin and co-workers reported a pioneer work on the formation of correlated defect nano-regions on an archetypical UiO-66(Hf) material, by combining experimental and computational methods. In particular, the use of diffuse and anomalous X-ray scattering together with xPDF analyses, demonstrated the occurrence of correlated defects with no significant change in the local structure of the Hf-clusters.³⁵ More recently, De Vos and co-workers showed the application

of xPDF analyses to demonstrate a different disorder state occurring on a flexible UiO-66(Zr) analogue. In this work, xPDF analyses were critical to identify variations on the intra-cluster Zr...Zr distances, confirming the remarkable *breathing* of this framework.³⁶

The structural characterization of non-crystalline MOF systems lacking of crystals simply cannot be faced by applying traditional crystallographic approaches. These materials do not show Bragg peaks neither in a powder neutron nor X-ray diffraction experiment since they lack of long-range ordering. Instead, the diffuse scattering signal, which contains information on atom-atom correlations can be analysed to elucidate the short and intermediate range ordering within these systems. Thus, PDF analyses have emerged as a powerful characterization probe to unveil the local structure of non-ideal MOF materials lacking of long-range ordering.

Fig. 2 a) PDF pattern for UiO-66 (dark blue) and amorphous UiO-66 (light blue). A–F labels of peaks below 8 Å correspond to the indicated correlations in the $Zr_6O_4(OH)_4$ cluster (inset). b) Two Zr-clusters linked by a terephthalic acid ligand, and some of the significant distances corresponding to the longer r features (G–K) in (a). Zr – light blue, O – red, C – gray, H – omitted for clarity. Reprinted from Ref. ³⁴ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

The variety of non-crystalline MOFs is remarkable. These materials are usually categorized depending on the method used for their preparation: amorphous (non-glassy), liquids and glasses.^{37,38} Amorphous (non-glassy) MOFs are typically obtained by addition of modulators during the synthesis³⁹ or post-synthetically, via controlled heating treatments²⁸ or pressure.^{40,41} An important subset of MOF materials, the zeolite imidazolate frameworks (ZIFs),⁴² have shown great potential to form liquid phases upon heating. After the first example of MOF melting for the ZIF-4 [$Zn(Im)_2$] (Im = imidazolate) framework reported by Bennett *et al.* in 2015,⁴³ several interesting works appeared in the recent literature. According to this pioneer work, a liquid MOF is defined as a liquid formed from the melting of a MOF, retaining the chemical configuration and Zn–Im–Zn bonding network, characteristic of the crystalline phase.

Liquid MOFs are obtained through melting at moderated temperatures of a crystalline native phase, without resulting in the formation of derivate metal-oxides.⁴⁴ Liquid MOFs are of particular interest not only from a fundamental structural point of view but also for industry – porous liquids are envisaged as promising alternative technologies to their solid analogues for liquid-gas separations.⁴⁵ MOF glasses^{46,38} can be directly obtained either through rapid cooling of a liquid MOF⁴³ or through mechano-synthesis using ball-milling.⁴⁷

Recently, Coudert, Bennett and co-workers⁴⁸ reported the *in-situ* melting of ZIF-4, followed by PDF analyses (combining X-rays and neutrons) and Reverse Monte Carlo (RMC) modelling. Total scattering data confirmed the absence of Bragg peaks for both the liquid and glass phases, in agreement with their amorphous nature. Upon heating the ZIF-4 glass from 304 to 778 K, the intensity and position of the first sharp signal seen in the total scattering X-ray data remained unaltered. Interestingly, further heating up to 856 K resulted a significant intensity reduction and a shift in the first sharp diffraction peak, along with the near-total disappearance of the characteristic high Q -values features seen for crystalline ZIF-4. Importantly, the structural rearrangements occurring during the formation of the liquid MOF are assessed with theoretical calculations. First-principles molecular dynamic (FPMD) simulations were performed at different temperatures ranging from 300 up to 2250 K, demonstrating that ZIF-4 porosity is retained in its liquid form. To probe the generic nature of the ZIF melting, the authors also discussed the high-temperature behaviour of ZIF-8 computationally – this MOF does not melt experimentally since decomposition occurs at a lower temperature than melting. Importantly, authors in this work demonstrated that liquid MOFs are indeed porous – this remarkable finding makes them ideal candidates for molecular separations where diffusion is challenging.

The mixed-linker framework ZIF-62 [$Zn(Im)_{1.75}(blm)_{0.25}$] (blm = benzimidazolate) melts at 710 K giving a liquid, which further results in a melt-quenched glass after cooling at 591 K.⁴⁹ ZIF-62 has demonstrated an exceptional ability to form glasses in a wide range of compositions [$Zn(Im)_{2-x}(blm)_x$].⁵⁰ In this work, Yue and co-workers applied PDF analyses to assess the local- and intermediate-range order within the ZIF-62 glasses. The PDF studies demonstrated that, while both intra- and inter- Zn_4 -cluster correlations are seen in the crystalline phase, only the peaks linked to distances within the Zn_4 -cluster are retained in the glass. This result corroborated that the local structure of ZIF-62 is entirely preserved in its glass form. The glass-behaviour of the ZIF-62 topology is indeed not only restricted to Zn-based SBUs. Similar glass-formation has been recently reported for ZIF-62(Co) at 705 K by applying xPDF analyses while retaining almost 50% of the native porosity in the crystalline system.⁵¹

Further exploiting liquid MOFs, ZIF materials with different topologies and chemistries can blend together resulting in a homogeneous mixed phase, as shown for ZIF-4 and -62.⁵² In this work, the chemical structure of a ZIF blend was explored by applying both neutron and synchrotron X-ray total scattering. X-ray diffraction data collected on a physical mixture containing

crystalline ZIF-4_{Co} and ZIF-62 in a 1 to 1 molar ratio showed Bragg peaks, while the corresponding blend [(ZIF-4-Co)_{0.5}(ZIF-62)_{0.5}] did not. PDF data collected on the mixed blend demonstrated, however, that the non-crystalline system has identical local structure than that of its crystalline analogue, with similar PDF features up to *ca.* 8 Å.

Recently, flux-melting has been proved as a promising methodology to access to liquid phases of MOFs whose melting temperatures cannot be achieved before decomposition. This is the case of ZIF-8 [Zn(MeIm)₂] (MeIm = 2-methylimidazolate), which can be melt using liquid ZIF-62 as a solvent.⁵³ By performing small- and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS and WAXS, respectively) experiments under flux melting conditions, the authors could monitor the melting of the ZIF-8 phase at 650 K with the corresponding disappearance of the Bragg peaks. PDF data collected on the final alloy-glassy [(ZIF-8)_{0.2}(ZIF-62)_{0.8}] material corroborated that the short-range order is preserved upon flux-melting, showing characteristic signals linked to Zn–Zn correlations up to *ca.* 8 Å. Further expanding this concept, an example of MOF-crystal-glass composite [(MIL-53)_{0.25}(ZIF-62)_{0.75}] has been reported.⁵⁴ In this composite material, MIL-53 maintains its crystallinity upon heating, while ZIF-62 melts and subsequently vitrifies. PDF data showed that the local structures of both MIL-53 and ZIF-62 are retained in the composite while lacking of long-range order, with atom-atom correlations observed up to *ca.* 11 Å.

Fig. 3 a, Schematic of flux melted glass formation of (ZIF-8)(ZIF-62)(20/80) and $a_g[(ZIF-8)_{0.2}(ZIF-62)_{0.8}]$; b, Comparison of the atomic configuration, *ca.* 50 Å³, of (right) a high-temperature liquid ZIF obtained from computational, and experimental neutron and synchrotron pair distribution function modelling and the unit cell of ZIF-8; c, Structure factors $S(q)$ and; d, X-ray pair distribution functions $D(r)$ of ZIF-8, (ZIF-8)(ZIF-62)(20/80), $a_g[(ZIF-8)_{0.2}(ZIF-62)_{0.8}]$ and $a_gZIF-62$, respectively. Adapted from Ref.⁵³ with permission from The Royal Society of Chemistry.

2.2. Disrupting periodicity through chemistry: local modifications on MOF materials

MOF materials have been used in a wide range of applications of molecular nature with excellent results, proving mandatory to harness and understand their chemistries and structures to tailor their final performance. One of the most relevant applications of MOFs is related to their high gas uptake capacity, given the unique porosity of these materials.^{55,56} Chapman, Morris and co-workers have extensively studied interactions between gas molecules and MOFs using xPDF analyses.^{57,58}

More recently, Nenoff and co-workers evaluated the selective O₂ uptake over N₂ at ambient temperatures of an archetypical large-pore MIL-100(Sc) composed of trimeric Sc(III)–oxo clusters.⁵⁹ The authors reported a modelling-directed experimental study, showing that O₂ is more favourably adsorbed than N₂ over a wide temperature range (*i.e.* 77 K – 313 K) for MIL-100(Sc). Interestingly, while X-ray diffraction showed similar average structures for both materials, differential PDF (dPDF) analyses demonstrated a significantly different structural scenario at the local-scale. dPDF profiles, obtained after subtracting the PDF of the organic ligand to that of MIL-100 systems, retrieved the atom-atom correlations exclusively linked to the metal-oxo clusters. Thus, for MIL-100(Sc), a shift to longer distances was observed for the Sc–O and Sc...Sc distances within the trimeric clusters, compared to the regular cluster geometry seen in MIL-100(Fe). This result is in agreement with a local distortion occurring within the clusters linked to an out-of-plane configuration, allowing closer proximity of O₂ to and subsequent interaction with Sc versus Fe. This work exemplifies well the application of dPDF analyses to identify subtle local distortions within MOF clusters.

The high and versatile porosity of MOFs has been also exploit for capturing hazardous chemicals in the last years.^{60,61} The PDF technique has been proved to be a unique tool to understand the interactions occurring between these materials and toxic guest species in the pores. Farha and co-workers reported the removal of Sb(OH)₆⁻ from water using the mesoporous NU-1000 material composed of Zr(IV)–oxo clusters.⁶² The dPDF data, obtained after subtracting the PDF of the pristine MOF to that of the samples after capturing Sb(OH)₆⁻, revealed new atom-atom correlations at *ca.* 1.97 Å linked to Sb–O distances and at *ca.* 3.45 Å and 3.72 Å associated with Sb...Zr distances, demonstrating the actual binding of Sb(OH)₆⁻ species to the Zr(IV)–oxo clusters in a η₂μ₂ mode (Fig. 4). In a related previous work,⁶³ the authors showed a similar PDF approach to demonstrate the structural mechanism for the capture of selenate and selenite species from water on NU-1000.

Fig. 4 (a) Experimental and calculated dPDF data of NU-1000 after Sb(OH)₆⁻ adsorption and (b) Zr(IV)-node model of NU-1000 with Sb(OH)₆⁻ bonding. Reprinted from reference.⁶² Copyright © 2018, with permission from Elsevier.

Due to the reticular nature of MOF architectures, mixed-metal approaches have been explored to develop new materials with tailored properties depending on their applications.^{64,65} In

2019, Kieslich, Fischer and co-workers reported a novel Cu/Zn mixed pillared-layered MOF with tailored flexibility.⁶⁶ Due to the lack of crystals, PDF was the only way to demonstrate the simultaneous incorporation of Cu and Zn within the MOF clusters. By applying PDF analyses, the authors identified signals at *ca.* 2.0–2.1 Å and *ca.* 2.92 Å, linked to M–N,O and M...M distances within the clusters, respectively. PDF profiles also showed a broader signal linked to M...M distances for those MOFs prepared with a high content of copper, pointing towards the occurrence of expected Jahn-Teller distortion within the copper-containing clusters.

Atomic layer deposition (ALD) in MOFs (named as AIM method)⁶⁷ has emerged as a versatile method to decorate robust MOF platforms with added metal-oxo nanoclusters.⁶⁸ ALD-modified MOF materials, however, often lack of crystals, hindering their structural analyses by conventional diffraction techniques. In 2017, Chapman and co-workers studied the local structure of a nickel-ALD-modified NU-1000 material active in hydrogenation of light olefins, by combining PDF analyses with Ni *K*-edge Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) spectroscopy and Density Functional Theory (DFT) modelling.¹⁶ dPDF data of Ni-NU-1000, obtained by subtracting the PDF of the pristine NU-1000 material, indicated the presence of new signals at *ca.* 2.03 Å and 3.03 Å linked to Ni–O and Ni...Ni distances, respectively. An additional signal at *ca.* 3.26 Å linked to Ni...Zr distances was observed, proving the attachment of the Ni₄O_xH nanoclusters to the Zr₆-clusters of the MOF. By combining these PDF results with modelling and EXAFS analyses (Fig. 5), the authors hypothesized that the local structure of the ALD-deposited Ni₄O_xH clusters within NU-1000 resembles that of α -Ni(OH)₂. Additionally, Difference Envelope Density (DED) analyses⁶⁹ were carried out to determine the location and orientation of the Ni₄O_xH clusters within the material. These results demonstrated that the added nickel-oxo species are located within the small pores, by bridging the Zr₆-clusters, giving the formation of heterobimetallic Ni–Zr–O nanowires in the MOF.

Fig. 5 Multiple models of a Ni₄ cluster attached to a MOF Zr₆-oxo cluster and a comparison of the corresponding simulated Ni *K*-edge EXAFS (left) and PDFs (right, Ni–Ni, Ni–O, and O–O correlations) to the experimental data (black). Model C provides the best match to the experimental data, for both EXAFS and PDF [C: light gray, O: red, Ni: green,

Zr: gray]. Reprinted with permission from Ref.¹⁶ Copyright© (2017) American Chemical Society.

Alternatively, solvent-assisted ligand exchange (SALE)⁷⁰ is a versatile approach to chemically modify MOF materials with both metal-complexes and organic linkers. Platero-Prats, Chapman, Martín-Matute and co-workers reported a SALE modification of the dynamic Zn-bio-MOF-1000⁷¹ material with an iridium complex.⁷² The authors demonstrated the local structure and distribution of the iridium-complexes within the MOF structure by combining dPDF and Ir *L*_{III}-edge EXAFS analyses. dPDF data, obtained by subtracting the PDF of pristine bio-MOF-100 to those of the Ir-modified MOFs, revealed new peaks at *ca.* 2.20 Å and 2.35 Å associated with Ir–N and Ir–Cl distances within the iridium complex, respectively. Interestingly, the intensity of these dPDF signals increases with the amount of iridium complex incorporated in the MOF (Fig. 6), with no evidence for the formation of IrO₂ nano-clusters as sub-product. Unexpectedly, dPDF analyses also revealed intermediate-range correlations in the range of *ca.* 6–10 Å linked to Ir...Ir distances between different iridium-complexes, proving the distribution pattern of the chemical modification at high iridium contents (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Bio-MOF-100 functionalized with an iridium complex: **a)** differential PDFs of the MOFs containing increasing amounts of iridium complex and **b)** structural model. Adapted with permission from Ref. ⁷² Copyright© 2017 American Chemical Society.

2.3. Following *in-situ* MOF chemistry and catalysis at the local scale

MOF architectures have been widely explored as catalytic materials for a variety of chemical processes,^{73,74} given their rich structural and chemical nature. Being catalysis a highly localized phenomenon, PDF is a unique structural tool to gain knowledge about the occurrence of defects within MOFs at a short-range upon chemical modifications as well as during reaction. Indeed, subtle alterations of order within MOF structures, occurring at a short-scale and under conditions relevant for catalysis, might play a key in boosting chemical reactions.^{75,27}

In 2019, Bhan, Gagliardi and co-workers reported on the structure, dynamics and reactivity of MIL-100(Fe) in the oxidation of light alkanes.⁷⁶ To understand the potential local

structural implications of activation and catalysis in this MOF, PDF data was collected on the as-synthesized material, after heated at the 523 K and after reaction. dPDFs were obtained after subtracting the PDF of the organic ligand, thereby highlighting the correlations exclusively assigned to the Fe₃-oxo-cluster. dPDF analyses performed on the activated MIL-100(Fe) system indicated a subtle shift to lower *r*-values of the signals linked to Fe–O, Fe⋯Fe and Fe–C distances, together with a decrease in intensity of the signal associated with Fe–O bonds. This result is in agreement with the reduction in the average iron coordination number upon activation. Interestingly, dPDF analyses showed that both bond distances and coordination number is partially recovered after catalysis. Moreover, PDF analyses corroborated to lack of formation of parasite iron nanoclusters, thereby demonstrated the actual active species to be the isolated Fe₃-oxo-clusters.

The possibility of studying MOF materials under real working conditions, *in-situ*, by using fast and high-energy synchrotron X-rays offers the unique opportunity of providing a more realistic picture of kinetics linked to synthesis and catalysis occurring in the short- and intermediate-range scales. Pioneer work on the use of *in-situ* PDF studies to assess metal nanoparticle⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰ and coordination polymer⁸¹ growth as well as assembling mechanisms observed in germanates,⁸² to mention few, can be found in the literature. Thallapally, Billinge and co-workers recently reported on the initial stages of nucleation for ZIF-8, [Zn(Melm)₂] (Melm = 2-methylimidazolate).⁸³ *In-situ* PDF experiments were performed at room temperature by mixing the precursors, that is aqueous Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and methanolic Melm, using a liquid flow cell. The challenging dPDF analyses performed in this work (*i.e.* use of liquids, low sample concentration) revealed the unexpected formation of stable monomers of Zn(Melm)₄ at the early stages of reaction. While reaction evolves, the formation of Zn_x(Melm)_y aggregates together with an amorphous intermediate phase was identified, prior to the MOF crystallization. These *in-situ* PDF experiments were carried out under realistic synthesis conditions, highlighting the complexity of growth mechanisms in MOFs.

In 2019, Iversen and co-workers explored nucleation processes of the archetypical UiO-66 material composed of Zr₆O₈ clusters.⁸⁴ The *in-situ* experiments were performed loading the precursor solutions into a fused silica capillary reactor, pressurized to 103 bar and heated to a temperature of 150 °C.⁸⁵ Interestingly, *in-situ* PDF analyses demonstrated the appearance of signals linked to Zr⋯Zr characteristic of the hexamer cluster without addition of organic ligand nor modulator (Fig. 7). This is certainly an unpredicted result, since tetramers or extended oligomer chains are generally accepted to be the most stable phases in solution.

Fig. 7 a) PDFs data illustrating the reaction progress at 150 °C.; b) Example of an experimental setup. In this case, the synchrotron X-ray beam is monochromatized, hits the nanoparticles inside the reactor, and gets scattered onto the 2D detector. The reactor is heated by a jet of hot air and pressurized by water.; c) Evolution of the structure of the species detected by PDF during nucleation and early growth of UiO-66 nanoparticle. a) and c) adapted with permission from Ref. ⁸⁴ Copyright 2019 John Wiley and Sons. b) Reprinted with permission from Ref. ⁸⁰ Copyright© (2012) American Chemical Society.

Local structural rearrangements occurring during MOF activation upon heating, without changing the average MOF structure, was firstly assessed by *in-situ* PDF analyses by Chapman and co-workers.⁸⁶ The authors described the occurrence of a local phase transition within ubiquitous M₆O₈ clusters (M = Hf or Zr) induced by heating, for two archetypical MOF architectures, UiO-66 and NU-1000. The *in-situ* PDF experiments were performed by loading the MOF into a gas flow cell under He atmosphere and heating at controlled rate to mimic activation conditions. The observed structural transition, occurring exclusively at the local scale and without compromising the average MOF structure, resembles that of bulk MO₂ oxides. Interestingly, due to the nano-sized nature of the cluster and confinements effects, the transition occurs in a reversed order (*i.e.* from regular to distorted upon heating) and at significantly low temperatures (*i.e.* at 120 °C), compared to their bulk analogues. bulk analogues at much higher temperature. Local insights from PDF analyses are complement with DFT modelling to provide accurate structural periodic models of the NU-1000 MOF, after activation.

In-situ PDF studies have been recently applied to elucidate the activation mechanism of catalytically active metal nanoparticles deposited in the NU-1000 MOF composed of Zr₆O₈ clusters. Chapman and co-workers reported the local structure of ALD-deposited Cu(II)-oxo clusters within NU-1000 MOF.⁸⁷ Additionally, the authors performed *in-situ* PDF experiments under H₂ atmosphere at 200 °C to chase the formation of catalytically active Cu⁰ nanoparticles (Fig. 8). Subsequently, after re-exposing the material to air, Cu₂O nanoparticles are formed. Furthermore, DED analyses were

applied to identify the distribution of the copper catalytic species within the MOF under activation conditions, demonstrating that they are highly mobile (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. a) PDF data of pristine Cu-AIM, at the beginning and end of reduction at 200 °C a following re-oxidation upon exposure to air. b) DED maps viewed parallel (top) and perpendicular (bottom) to the c-axis for Cu-AIM in the pristine state, at the beginning and end of reduction at 200 °C and following re-oxidation.⁸⁷ Adapted from Ref. ⁸⁷ with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.

3. Conclusions and Perspectives

In this minireview, we discussed recent advances in the applications of PDF analyses to the structural characterization of *non-ideal* MOF materials. This is indeed a current challenge in the field: how can one address the incisive structural study of a MOF lacking of crystals? We summarized outstanding recent work on non-crystalline MOFs, ranging from amorphous matter and glasses to liquids. In this context, X-ray and neutron PDF analyses combined with computational studies, have been proved to be a powerful tool to determine local and intermediate-range structures of highly disordered frameworks. We also provided insights into recent work on the characterization of defective-MOF materials, where variations of ordering exclusively occur at the local scale without disrupting the average structure (typically studied by diffraction techniques). This is indeed an emerging field of research, where periodicity is selectively disrupted through chemistry to tailor MOF properties towards enhanced ultimate applications. In this context, we discussed the use of d-PDF analyses, which highlight new atom–atom distances within a given material (*i.e.* added catalytic metal-oxo species in the MOF pores) as well as subtle local distortions (*i.e.* local structural transitions within MOF clusters). Regarding the differential analyses of PDF data, we

think that the current challenge is to develop robust methods to extract and to fit the experimental d-PDF data using molecular modelling. Finally, we stressed the importance of *in-situ* PDF studies to follow MOF synthesis, activation and catalytic activity under realistic working conditions. We are convinced that the consolidation of dedicated PDF beamlines at main large facilities together with the development of specific PDF cells to perform *in-situ* experiments, will bring many exciting and unpredicted structural findings in the next years in the field of MOF materials lacking of long-range ordering. Beyond this aspect, we think that the PDF technique will consolidate in the next future as the definitive structural probe to unveil local interactions occurring on MOFs during phenomena of molecular nature, such as catalysis and separation, under working conditions.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

We thank the Spanish Government (RTI2018-096138-A-I00) and the Regional Government of Madrid (TALENTO grant 2017-T1/IND5148) for funding. C. C. B. acknowledges the European Social Funds and the Regional Government of Madrid for a postdoctoral contract (PEJD-2018-POST/IND-7909). I. R. M. acknowledges the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid for predoctoral fellowship.

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